
ANALYSIS OF METHODS FOR INCREASING OIL RECOVERY OF HIGH-VISCOSITY OIL FIELDS.

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Abstract.

Oil recovery, or the level of extraction of underground oil reserves, to a significant extent affects the size of important investments in prospecting and exploration drilling, and also in drawing up a plan for the growth of industrial, promising and predictive reserves. In addition, understanding the true value of oil recovery is of great importance in order to score vanishing reserves, the productivity of the exploration concepts used, the possibilities and extent of the introduction of new exploration methods in long-term developed deposits.

Key words.

Oil recovery, oil deposits, intensification, black gold.

Introduction

Oil recovery depends on the geological circumstances of the occurrence of oil in the subsoil, the heterogeneity of the reservoirs, the material qualities of the reservoirs and the fluids held in them, the concept of research and the method of influencing in a row, and also on the margin of financial profitability of well operation. The production of oil is bound to increase in no way only because of the result of putting the newest deposits into use, but also because of the result of increasing the oil recovery of the developed fields. The number of disappearing oil, according to the structure of the deposits, is determined by tens and hundreds of millions of tons. A slight increase in oil recovery is tantamount to the invention of some large fields. Financial conclusions associated with obtaining additional oil production and the use of field facilities will become large. In a similar way, the

direction of enhanced oil recovery, i.e. solving the problem of the greatest extraction of oil from the subsoil is considered one of the biggest economic problems.

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Review of modern methods of enhanced oil recovery.

The effectiveness of extracting oil from oil-bearing formations by advanced, industrially studied methods of research in absolutely all oil-producing states at the present time is insufficient, in addition to the fact that the use of petroleum products in absolutely the entire society has been increasing over the years. The average ultimate oil recovery is from 25 to 40%. in connection with the texture of the oil reserves and the methods of exploration used. Residual or non-recoverable by industrially studied methods of research, oil reserves usually reach 55-75% of the initial geological reserves of oil in the bowels. The main reasons for the current situation are: - significant depletion (70%) of active reserves as a result of their many years of intensive selective mining; - rapid growth in the share of hard-to-recover reserves (60-65%); 12 - in reducing the efficiency of technological indicators of field development using traditional water flooding. The study and synthesis of the world and Russian skill of reproducing the raw material basis of oil production demonstrates that the leading rate of increase in oil reserves in our time will be innovative methods of enhanced oil recovery (EOR), in particular, built-in technological processes that combine a combination of different methods (thermal, gas and physico-chemical). The distribution of the vanishing oil saturation of the reservoirs will require that the methods of enhanced oil recovery effectively operate

in black gold, inattentive in flooded or gassed areas of the reservoirs, in other low-permeable reservoirs and interlayers with a significant current oil saturation in indivisible flooded layers, and in addition to isolated lenses and areas of the layer, absolutely not covered by drainage, the presence of the existing production concept. It is absolutely indisputable that the presence of such a vast variety of disappearing reserves of capital, and in addition, the presence of a huge difference in the qualities of oil, water, gas and the permeability of oil-saturated formation bands is in no way able to be the first multi-purpose method of increasing oil recovery. Known methods of enhanced oil recovery are mainly characterized by a directional effect and affect a maximum of one or two factors that affect the state of residual reserves. Let's consider the classification of the main methods of enhanced oil recovery. Group of combined methods. From the point of view of the impact on the reservoir system, in most cases, it is the combined principle of impact that is implemented, which combines hydrodynamic and thermal methods, hydrodynamic and physico-chemical methods, thermal and physico-chemical methods, and so on. Methods for increasing the flow rate of wells. These are mainly physical methods for increasing well production rates. Combining them with enhanced oil recovery methods is not entirely correct due to the fact that the use of enhanced oil recovery methods is characterized by an increased potential of the displacing agent, and in physical methods, the potential of the oil displacing agent is realized through the use of natural reservoir energy. In addition, physical methods most often do not increase the ultimate oil recovery of the reservoir, but only lead to a temporary increase in production, that is, an increase in the current oil recovery of the reservoir. The most commonly used physical methods include:

- hydraulic fracturing;
- horizontal wells;
- electromagnetic influence;
- wave action on the formation. Consider the technology of methods for enhanced oil recovery.

Thermal EOR are methods for intensifying oil inflow and increasing the productivity of production wells, based on an artificial increase in temperature in their well-bore and bottom hole zone. Thermal EOR are used mainly in the production of high-viscosity paraffinic and resinous oils. Heating leads to oil liquefaction, melting of paraffin and resinous substances that have settled during the operation of wells on the walls, lifting pipes and in the bottom hole zone. A) Steam-thermal effect on the formation. Steam flooding is an enhanced oil recovery technique most commonly used to drive 15 high-viscosity oils. In this process,

steam is injected from the surface into formations with low temperature and high viscosity of oil through special steam injection wells located inside the oil-bearing contour. Steam, which has a high heat capacity, introduces a significant amount of thermal energy into the reservoir, which is spent on heating the reservoir and reducing the relative permeability, viscosity and expansion of all agents that saturate the reservoir - oil, water, gas.

Conclusion

With the abstract use of different events in the field, according to the increase in the oil recovery of the layer, the production of oil significantly increases and, at the end of the points, leads to financial benefits and makes it possible to apply natural remedies in the most detailed and environmentally friendly way. This makes it possible to offer the examined scientific and technical event for introduction in standard oil and gas fields his relationship to his own obligations, to the surrounding sphere in absolutely all degrees. There are a large number of omissions, and a continuous increase in the degree of environmental knowledge, environmental culture simply follows.

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